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*A THEORETICAL ANALYSIS ON LEADERSHIP TYPES AND
GENERATIONAL DIVERSITY IN ENTREPRENEURIAL ORGANIZATIONS¹*

**UMA ANÁLISE TEÓRICA SOBRE OS TIPOS DE LIDERANÇA E A
DIVERSIDADE GERACIONAL NAS ORGANIZAÇÕES EMPREENDEDORAS**

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ABSTRACT

In the academic literature on leadership and management, the idea that there are demonstrable generational differences in attitudes, motivation and behavior at work is so widespread as to border on the axiomatic. Thus, there are several strong assumptions about how generations operate in the workplace and, in particular, how they influence leadership processes and outcomes. Thus, the objective of this article is to explore the mutual influence between this dyad and enrich the literature in the area of leadership and multigenerational interactions at work based on a theoretical analysis of current literature on this topic. With that said, it is demonstrated that workers from different generational groups want and/or need different forms of leadership to achieve optimal performance.

Keywords: leadership, multigenerational interactions, workplace behavior.

RESUMO

Na literatura acadêmica sobre liderança e gestão, a ideia de que existem diferenças geracionais demonstráveis em atitudes, motivação e comportamento no trabalho é tão difundida que beira o axiomático. Desta forma, existem vários pressupostos fortes sobre como as gerações operam no local de trabalho e, em particular, como influenciam os processos e resultados de liderança. Assim, o objetivo deste artigo é explorar a influência mútua entre essa díade e enriquecer a literatura na área de liderança e interações multigeracionais no trabalho a partir de uma análise teórica da literatura atual sobre este tema. Com isso posto, é demonstrado que trabalhadores de diferentes cortes geracionais desejam e/ou

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RELISE

243

necessitam de diferentes formas de liderança para alcançar um desempenho ideal.

Palavras-chave: liderança, interações multigeracionais, comportamento no trabalho.

RELISE

244

INTRODUCTION

Generations are the product of historical events that leave powerful emotional memories shaping feelings about authority, institutions, and family (TWENGE, 2023; RUDOLPH et al., 2021). Generational strengths can reduce morale-control costs, decrease turnover, and increase sales and profits. It is essential to be aware of generational differences because, in the 21st century, generations coexist in the same workplace more than ever before, thanks to the emergence of new work relationships derived from modern entrepreneurial organizational structures (GEORGESCU; BODISLAV, 2024; ENGESTRÖM; SANNINO, 2021).

The workforce in entrepreneurial organizations is currently highly diverse. The mix of race, gender, and ethnicity within organizations has now become indispensable (ZHAO et al., 2021; ELY; THOMAS, 2020). Forward-looking organizations, recognizing the potential of diversity, have developed and implemented strategic plans that leverage this diversification to become more competitive in the global economy (LI; SHEMLA; WEGGE, 2021; ELY; THOMAS, 2020). However, there is one important factor that is often misunderstood or even ignored when discussing diversity: generational difference. This confusion and the inability to appreciate generational differences have created popular stereotypes and criticism from both the media and academia regarding their relevance for dialogue between different generations and for the leadership styles adopted in entrepreneurship-oriented organizations (SCHIUMA et al., 2022; HANSON; KEPLINGER, 2022).

On the one hand, the sharing of different perspectives across generations fosters creativity and innovation. On the other hand, negative interactions arise from points of conflict when misunderstandings between generations create unnecessary personal and organizational disputes. The misunderstanding and underestimation of generational differences stem from the traditional but

RELISE

245

mistaken belief that people change values, attitudes, and preferences based on age.

Therefore, it is important to emphasize that leadership is a process of social influence in which the leader seeks the voluntary participation of subordinates in an effort to achieve organizational goals, a process by which a person exerts social influence over other group members, a process of influencing the activities of an individual or group of individuals in an effort to achieve goals in specific situations, and a relational concept involving both the influencing agent and the influenced person (ZHANG et al., 2021; UDOVITA, 2020). Effective leadership is the extent to which a leader continuously and progressively guides and directs followers toward the agreed-upon destination defined by the entire group (SIMS, 2021; BEN SEDRINE; BOUDERBALA; NASRAOUI, 2021).

The available literature in the field of generational diversity in the workplace is minimal. However, research is increasing to better understand intergenerational diversity at work (IQBAL, 2024). The purpose of this article is to explore the management dilemma that exists in the workplace and to enrich the literature in the field of leadership and multigenerational workplace interactions. The literature review presented in this study was designed to illustrate the need for further research in the area of generational diversity and the importance of leaders recognizing and adapting to this diversity in order to address this growing phenomenon in the work environment. Furthermore, the researchers of this article describe several types of leadership, so that an analysis can be made on the possibility of leaders adapting within entrepreneurial organizations.

GENERATIONAL DIVERSITY

The concept of generation can be understood through various perspectives by means of studies from authors who have focused on this theme.

RELISE

246

According to Colet and Mozzato (2019), a generation is composed of individuals born in the same time period who, therefore, share the same experiences and are shaped by the context in which they live. The differences in habits and customs among today's generations of people are noticeable, and this is reflected in contemporary entrepreneurial organizations. Furthermore, the analysis of the term generation can be carried out by highlighting the general historical events experienced by people of the same age group, which help explain the behaviors and actions of this group of individuals (COLET; MOZZATO, 2021).

In contrast, Bezerra et al. (2019) argue that the definition of generation goes beyond equality of age and a given period of time to determine belonging to a specific generation. People, regardless of whether they were born in the same era, are influenced by their current experiences and, therefore, may circulate among different generations. The disparity between generations attracts considerable interest regarding human capital and organizational practices (PANDITA, 2022). Research suggests that generational differences influence personal values, behaviors and popular beliefs, workspaces, ethical ideologies, and employee engagement. Generational differences also affect leisure and extrinsic values (RAFIKI; HARTIJASTI, 2022).

In this sense, it becomes evident that the workplace is filled with numerous workers from different generations. With distinct perspectives, cultures, and approaches to carrying out their activities, the organizational climate becomes prone to internal conflicts if not given proper attention (TEIXEIRA, 2022). Carioni and Dutra (2024) identify that workplace conflict arises from several factors, among which differences in expectations and communication styles stand out.

The literature identifies four generations that currently occupy space in the labor market, each with its own characteristics according to its chronological period of birth, and also makes reference to technological advances as a key

RELISE

247

factor distinguishing them in terms of thoughts and behaviors about the work environment (CRUZ; SILVA; LEITE, 2019). These are: the Baby Boomer generation (born between 1946 and 1966), Generation X (born between 1967 and 1979), Generation Y (born between 1979 and 1995), and Generation Z (born between 1995 and 2010). Thus, considering the impact that generational diversity has on the workplace, although it can foster learning through the exchange of experiences among employees of different ages, on the other hand, if not managed properly, it can also negatively affect individual performance and, consequently, harm productivity (CARIONI; DUTRA, 2024).

TYPES OF LEADERSHIP

Autocratic leadership

Leadership in the field of management can be defined as the ability to persuade, motivate, and influence people to perform their work in the best possible way. It is linked to interpersonal communication to guide the team toward achieving established goals (SOUZA; MARQUES, 2019). The types of leadership are associated with how the leader relates to their subordinates in the organization, as well as how they use their power to make decisions. Several theories emphasize the leader's behavior toward their followers.

In the autocratic leadership model, the leader's decisions are fully centralized in themselves, leaving no freedom for employees to give input about the work. Activities are imposed and carried out in the presence of the leader (FERREIRA; MARTINS; SANTOS, 2021). The group merely follows the orders of their superior, being restricted from expressing any ideas. The leader demonstrates rigidity and authoritarianism, with little relationship between the two sides (MAGALHÃES; SOARES, 2019).

RELISE

248

Some individuals reflect on their professional careers and are able to identify specific leaders who had a positive impact and those who had a negative impact. A good leader can have lasting positive effects on an employee, just as a bad leader can negatively affect both the employee and the work environment. Wu et al. (2018) identify a connection between employees who experience destructive leadership and later adopt avoidance behavior. Likewise, Sulea et al. (2013) conducted a study with results indicating that employees who perceive their manager as abusive are more likely to engage in CWB. Both studies suggest that there is a behavioral response from employees depending on the leadership style.

According to Lewin et al. (1939), this is a strict leader who outlines the work; there is an element of the unknown for employees since this leader does not always provide all the necessary information and may appear somewhat indifferent toward them. This is a particularly interesting trait, as such a leader seems to withhold information for personal benefit - a form of power move. Workers do not have much freedom, and while this leader may achieve short-term success in terms of productivity and discipline, it tends to vanish since the leader is not always present. This can also affect trust between leader and employee (BLOOM; JONES; WOODCOCK, 2021).

Furthermore, Fiaz (2017) explains how this approach places greater emphasis on production and less on the employee, a concept based on the assumption that people are considered lazy and untrustworthy. Likert's management system (1961) describes autocratic leadership as an exploitative-authoritative structure in which direction and power come from the top, with poor communication and no regard for teamwork.

The autocratic leader relies on authority, control, and manipulation to complete the task or job at hand. Through this systematic leadership approach, penalties are imposed when mistakes are made, and sanctions may be applied

RELISE

249

by making employees feel guilty or withholding attention (ROSS; MATTESON; EXPOSITO, 2014). The motivation of an autocratic leader comes in the form of performance-based economic incentives, and development derives from hard work (FIAZ, 2017). Interestingly, according to a study by Singh et al. (2012), when considering some of the main themes identified in research on millennials in the workplace, feedback, inspiring leaders, and being part of a team were highlighted.

Democratic leadership

As with the definitions of leadership, the definitions of democratic leadership are also dynamic and abundant. For example, from 1938 to 1985, there were 29 different definitions and styles of democratic leadership. Luthans (1998) reviewed eight different styles of democratic leadership drawn from classical leadership studies and theories. These different definitions and styles have contributed to the absence of a clear and well-developed definition of democratic leadership (CHOI, 2007).

Although these various definitions and styles have focused only on the characteristics of democratic leadership within small groups and organizations, the literature has not paid attention to democratic leadership in the diverse context of democratic movements. Thus, it is essential that researchers address this issue, especially in different political, socioeconomic, and cultural situations and environments around the world (WOODS, 2021).

The democratic leadership approach, unlike the autocratic one where decisions are centralized in the leader, values the participation and engagement of collaborators in decision-making processes (GIMENES et al., 2019). The leader develops an interpersonal relationship with subordinates, task distribution is carried out by consensus, and the leader merely inspects and provides the necessary guidance (SOUZA; MARQUES, 2019).

RELISE

250

The notions of autocracy and democracy have been openly used to distinguish democratic leadership from autocratic leadership. Autocracy implies a high degree of control by leaders, with little freedom or participation by members in group decisions. Both democratic and laissez-faire leadership imply a low degree of control by the leader. However, democracy is distinguished from laissez-faire leadership by the fact that a democratic leader is highly active in stimulating discussion and group decisions, whereas a laissez-faire leader plays a passive and indifferent role (DLAMINI, 2018).

Democratic leadership is associated with increased productivity, satisfaction, engagement, and follower commitment. Member satisfaction and leadership appointments are higher under democratic leadership. Although significant disadvantages of democratic leadership include time-consuming activities and lengthy debates on policies, participation plays a key role in increasing leadership productivity (FAKHRI et al., 2021).

The definitions of democratic leadership conceptualized by White and Lippitt (1960) emphasize group participation, discussion, and group decisions encouraged by the leader. By contrast, an autocratic leader maintains strict control over group decisions and activities. The autocratic leader determines all policies, techniques, and stages of activity and dictates the specific work tasks and co-workers for each member. The autocratic leader tends to be personal in praising and criticizing each member's work but remains distant from active group participation (WILSON, 2020).

However, the democratic leader attempts to be a regular group member in spirit, without performing much work. While the main characteristic of the autocratic leader is to give orders, the main activity of the democratic leader is to provide information or broaden the knowledge of group members. In practice, the distinctions between the roles of autocratic and democratic leaders are not extreme. All roles of autocratic and democratic leaders remain within the normal

RELISE

251

range of leader behavior in different societal situations (ROSING; BOER; BUENGELER, 2022).

The characteristics of democratic leadership are defined as the distribution of responsibilities among members, the empowerment of group members, and assistance in the group's decision-making process. The varied characteristics of democratic leadership contribute to the lack of a clear definition of democratic leadership. Gastil (1994) argued that "the absence of a clear definition may also have contributed to the decline in the amount of research on democratic leadership" (p. 956).

Liberal leadership

Leadership styles are defined by the combination of leadership behaviors. The way a leader behaves in order to achieve a goal or perform a function determines what type of leadership behavior the leader adapts to. Some examples would be showing concern for a follower's personal feelings or providing information that helps the follower perform effectively (LANAJ; JENNINGS, 2020).

There are behavioral patterns that can be grouped according to the specificities of a given behavior. Therefore, the following leadership styles are identified by Howell and Costley (2006): coach, human relations specialist, controlling autocrat, transformational visionary, transactional exchange, and servant. Each leadership style is characterized by a set of leadership behaviors. For example, the coaching leadership style is highly directive and supportive, demonstrates concern and consideration, but also shows a need for power and affiliation. The human relations specialist leadership style exhibits the following behaviors: an emphasis on keeping followers happy and comfortable, generally not being directive with them, modifying the situation to make followers' work

RELISE

easier, etc. In contrast, the controlling autocrat style is highly directive with followers and dogmatic in its beliefs (HUNT; FITZGERALD, 2018).

In laissez-faire leadership, if a leader has any power, it is very limited. They give more freedom and independence to their subordinates. The task of these leaders is to determine the purposes and means of achieving them for their subordinates, while acting as a provider of information and as a contact with external environments. If the leader of an entrepreneurial organization - one fostered by creativity - were unquestionable, and employees had to obey without room for questions, answers, or critical attitudes toward workers' input, such an organization would not be a good place to foster creativity (LEE et al., 2020; COVIN; SLEVIN, 2017).

Thus, in environments where managers simply discourage workers' creativity by applying extreme abusive control in the workplace, the possibility of creative self-efficacy, ingenuity in decision-making, and job satisfaction will be reduced or entirely eliminated. In contrast, leaders who provide freedom to their subordinates and create additional incentives for them will succeed (ZHANG et al., 2020).

The results show that the best practice in organizational leadership for achieving the firm objectives of entrepreneurial organizations is to provide subordinates with freedom, create additional incentives - for example, by granting social benefits - welcome the production of innovative ideas by employees, and also provide professional recognition (KRYSCYNSKI; COFF; CAMPBELL, 2021). The new management objectives are to overcome traditional views that were leader-oriented and to create a perspective oriented toward fostering employee job satisfaction, as well as providing opportunities for workers to make decisions and building their confidence to nurture creative thoughts and ideas in a relaxed atmosphere (DURNALI; ORAKCI; KHALILI, 2023).

RELISE

253

This includes a creative and realistic atmosphere imposed by senior executive management, eventually rising to become the leadership of the organization's top management, so that more empowered and engaged employees are subject to the leaders' direction and all follow the organization's goals (HOANG; WILSON-EVERED; LOCKSTONE-BINNEY, 2021).

Thus, in laissez-faire leadership, there is greater freedom for employees to make their own decisions related to group work. The leader's participation is minimal, and their presence in the team is more tied to guidance than to giving orders (SILVA; ANTÔNIO, 2020). The leader allows the group to freely use their creativity and develop strategies, with no type of imposition or delegation of roles - everything is designated by the group (MAGALHÃES; SOARES, 2019).

Situational leadership

Situational leadership theory has been widely adopted as a model for leadership behavior and training. Acceptance of the theory seems to be based on its apparent validity. Research on situational leadership has focused on three main areas: the conceptual validity of the theory, the validity of its associated instrument - the Leadership Effectiveness and Adaptability Description (LEAD) survey - and the effect on subordinate performance when the theory is accurately practiced by the leader.

Situational leadership is the development of the leadership style proposed by Hapsari et al. (2021) to help leaders determine which leadership style is appropriate at a given moment. This theory is based on the interaction between the amount of direction a leader provides to subordinates, the amount of socioemotional support a leader offers, and, finally, the level of maturity subordinates demonstrate in a specific task. Hersey further explained that situational leadership theory could be applied in practice by leaders or managers to develop their human resources, that is, subordinates in ongoing organizations.

RELISE

254

The understanding of situational leadership is related to the adaptive behavior of the leader, which can be understood within the concept that the more a leader adapts their leadership behavior style to meet a particular situation, the more effectively they can influence subordinates to achieve both personal and organizational goals (Riyanto et al., 2021). Effective leadership is the backbone of any organization (Ayub et al., 2014). This leadership style is applied appropriately in a given situation (GHAZZAWI et al., 2017).

Thus, based on the behaviors observed, the leader may employ one of the three types of leadership (autocratic, democratic, or laissez-faire) that best fits the situation (SILVA; BARBOSA, 2021). In this regard, it is important that the leader possesses the knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary to identify which leadership style should be used according to the situation, since all present both strengths and weaknesses (SILVA; SANTOS; MARQUES, 2022).

TYPES OF GENERATIONS

Generation Y

Generation Y is characterized as those who are not bound by the teachings of the past and who are always seeking new knowledge for improvement. They are respectful and tolerant of differences in the job market, such as race, religion, and sexual orientation (URCO et al., 2019). In this sense, this generation easily accepts diversity and potential changes, with creativity and innovation being strong points of these individuals (SANTI et al., 2020).

Furthermore, Generation Y seeks flexibility and enjoyment at work, dynamism, quality of life, recognition, feedback, and interpersonal relationships. Due to the constant pursuit of enjoyment at work, this generation has been observed to continually change jobs (FOSSATTI; PAULI; TOMAS, 2021).

RELISE

255

Generation Z

Generation Z consists of people born from the mid-1990s to 2010. These individuals have been exposed to technological devices since birth, and for this reason they are strongly connected to the digital environment and handle current technological tools with ease. Thus, this is a generation that does not face difficulties in using internet-related tools; in other words, they did not need to adapt to the new technological trends that organizations demand as professional requirements (LIMA et al., 2022). Their high level of digital skills, having been born into this technological context, can be considered a positive aspect when viewed from one perspective. On the other hand, these individuals remain connected to social networks most of the time, mainly through mobile phone use, which ends up affecting their interpersonal relationships.

In the organizational environment, they are known as professionals who value flexibility, recognition for their work, rapid career advancement, autonomy, and social well-being within the company (COLET; MOZZATO, 2019).

These individuals are adept at multitasking and are stimulated by the technologies around them. Most often, they enjoy performing their tasks while listening to music through headphones. Other characteristics attributed to this generation include impatience when teaching, restlessness, difficulty accepting negative feedback from supervisors, and low concentration levels, as they are connected to social networks most of the time (BEZERRA et al., 2019).

THE MUTUAL INFLUENCE BETWEEN LEADERSHIP AND GENERATIONAL DIVERSITY IN ENTREPRENEURIAL ORGANIZATIONS

Generational differences within organizations inhibit the transfer of crucial information from managers in leadership positions to entry-level employees. This can be attributed to differences in the values, attitudes, and beliefs of each generation. The way leaders perceive generational differences

RELISE

256

and how each generation views its leaders can also create workplace challenges (Zemke et al., 2000). This manifests in the need for different leadership styles. Zemke et al. went further by indicating that different leadership styles are required to lead effectively in an atmosphere of generational diversity.

Different generations are present in organizations, constantly interacting with one another, which brings many challenges for people management. These are individuals with distinct purposes and perceptions, reflecting the broader context of the environments in which they grew up. In this context, leaders are challenged to understand the characteristics of each worker so they can foster optimal performance in the workplace.

Furthermore, Davenport and Prusak (2000) suggested that there is no single uniform leadership style. Indeed, successful leaders must adapt their leadership styles to meet the needs of their subordinates. Meredith, Schewe, and Hiam (2002) argued that these differences in values, attitudes, and beliefs require leadership styles that are flexible and capable of adapting to generational diversity. Thus, adjusting leadership styles and strategies to guide each group requires leaders to understand the generations present within a given organizational context.

Differences of opinion among individuals from different generations within organizations can lead to conflict, which, if properly managed, may become advantageous. In this regard, management plays a key role in diagnosing the characteristics of each individual within a work team to optimize collaboration and foster better interaction among members (COLET; MOZZATO, 2019).

Conflicts arising between generations can escalate to the point of high employee turnover within organizations, which results in the loss of highly skilled, productive, and talented professionals. Therefore, it is essential for managers to constantly assess the organizational climate so they can intervene at the right moment when necessary (SOARES, 2021). Each organization must therefore be

RELISE

257

aware of its work environment, particularly by recognizing the presence of generations ranging from the Baby Boomers to the so-called digital natives, Generation Z. The goal is to foster a balanced organizational climate free of conflicts that could lead to negative outcomes.

Encouraging employees from all generations to participate in this process is crucial, especially if an organization is facing generational challenges. As leaders tend to be older than their employees, they must recognize that younger generations want clear guidance and constructive feedback on their performance at a steady pace. Crampton and Hodge (2007) noted that the implications of multigenerational differences for general management practices have not yet been fully understood. Therefore, further research on leadership styles across generations is needed. Since Generation Z is just beginning to enter the workforce, it also requires examination by researchers and leaders in the social sciences. Hence, one of the responsibilities of leaders is to leverage employees to enhance productivity. Harnessing generational diversity and creating an environment in which leaders build constructive interactions with employees, while using their differences to strengthen organizational goals, should be the ultimate objective.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Aqui está a tradução completa para o inglês em tom formal e acadêmico:

According to what has been presented, the importance of studying generational diversity in the labor market has been observed, as understanding - or failing to understand - this point can be crucial to the success and commitment of leadership within an entrepreneurial organization. Therefore, it is necessary to recognize the individual traits and backgrounds that have led each generation to acquire such attributes. By understanding the characteristics of each generation present in the workplace, leaders will be able to design leadership strategies for

RELISE

258

each relevant aspect identified. In this way, leaders gain a clearer understanding of the actions and behaviors of subordinates, as well as how to properly respond to them.

Since there are various types of leadership, it is up to the leader to choose which is the most effective to apply to their generational audience. However, many authors affirm that there is no single correct leadership style. Thus, when it comes to generational diversity coexisting within the same work environment, leaders are required to adapt their leadership approach to achieve success in their management. Key generational differences that should be carefully assessed and not overlooked include communication and motivation. These two aspects must be evaluated with great caution, as one is linked to the other: the way a leader addresses their subordinates is an element that must be carefully considered in order to create a motivational effect within the leader–follower communication dynamic.

The younger generations currently entering the workforce - namely Generations Y and Z - are strongly connected to technology and digital environments. These generations have posed significant challenges for managers, as they bring strong workplace characteristics such as flexibility, innovation, and autonomy. In this context, the most suitable leadership style for employees with such attributes would be one that better addresses their motivational needs. Based on the literature, the leadership style most closely aligned with this is democratic leadership, as it emphasizes the participation of all members before any decision is made. Consequently, it provides greater freedom to foster creativity and the joint development of strategies by the team.

Although this topic has been gaining considerable visibility and importance for organizations today - given that it represents a management challenge requiring caution and a deep personal understanding - there are still few studies that provide solid evidence to support the recommendation of a single

RELISE

259

best leadership style for Generations Y and Z. These two generations, which occupy the largest share of job positions in current organizations and present high levels of complexity, are precisely those generating the most significant impacts.

RELISE

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RELISE

261

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RELISE

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